

MIND MAPPING IN ESSAYS

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Abstract: The study recommends an integration of the mind mapping strategy into the English as a foreign Language (EFL) curriculum at Universities as it facilitates developing students' writing skill. The study also recommends to examine the effect of using mind mapping strategy on EFL students' achievements in other language skills and sub skills. Teachers are also advised to use the mind mapping strategy to increase students' interest and motivation to write more often.

Key words: theoretical foundations, genre and discourse, cognitive load theory, discourse analysis.

Writing as a skill is very important in teaching and learning a foreign language; it helps pupils to assimilate letters and sounds of the English language, its vocabulary and grammar, and to develop habits and skills in *proThe skills-based approach views writing as a collection of separate skills, including letter formation, spelling, punctuation, grammar, organization, and the the like.* This approach also views writing as a product-oriented task. In this respect, McLaughlin state that writing, like many other complex tasks, requires "learners organize a set of related subtasks and their components". In contrast, the whole-language approach views writing as a meaning-making process which is governed by purpose and audience rather than by compositional rules pronunciation, speaking, and reading. In the area of EFL, writing has many uses and functions. To begin with, the ability to write acceptable scientific English is essential for post-graduate students who must write their dissertations in English. Moreover, writing EFL allows for communication to large numbers of people all

over the world. It also provides students with physical evidence of their achievement. This in turn helps them to determine what they know and what they don't know. Writing in general, second language writing in particular, can be an obstacle for some students. The reason why writing can be hard to learn is that writers face many challenges the moment they start writing. The challenges could be from gathering the ideas to be written, planning of the outline, focusing on sentence structure, choosing the appropriate expressions, and also making sure of the organization. Moreover, these challenges can cause students to have negative attitudes towards writing. Previous studies suggest that using writing strategies can help student control the writing process which have a positive effect on their writing achievement and their attitudes towards writing. The strategy of mind mapping is used as a pre-writing strategy to help writers visualize the structure of their writing. However, the researcher proposes using mind mapping strategy not only to organize ideas, but also to organize grammatical and linguistic knowledge. This study investigates the effect of using this mind mapping strategy as a pre-writing strategy to enhance female language learners' writing achievement and their attitudes towards writing in English at Taif University, Saudi Arabia. In a quasi-experimental design, a mixed methods approach was adopted by collecting quantitative and qualitative data. The study population is 128 students in an experimental group ($n_1= 57$) and a control group ($n_2=71$). The former received the treatment of instruction using mind mapping strategy and the latter received traditional instruction. The objectives of this study are first, to identify any differences between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group on post-tests of writing attitudes and writing achievement; second, to identify differences between the mean scores of the pre- and post-tests of writing attitudes and writing achievement for the experimental group; third, to explore students' views concerning difficulties to write in English. fourth, to identify the strategies they used to overcome these difficulties; fifth, to investigate if students

thought that mind mapping helped them write better and, if so, how. The researcher prepared a test to measure the writing achievement of female first-year EFL students, and a questionnaire by Sturm (1996) to measure writing attitudes. An interview was conducted with a focus group from the experimental group to achieve the third, fourth and fifth objectives.

Independent samples and paired sample t-tests were performed to quantitatively analyze data from the writing achievement test and the writing attitudes questionnaire. Data collected from the interview were qualitatively analyzed. The finding of the current study are first, there exists differences between the mean scores of the experimental and the control group on the post-tests of the students' writing achievement and writing attitudes, in favor of the experimental group; second there exists significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental group's pre- and post-tests in writing achievement and writing attitudes, in favor of the post-test; third, students' difficulties to write in English include lack of vocabulary, organization, spelling and grammar; fourth, students are accustomed to memorizing, practicing, and self-correcting, which indicates they are not used to planning their writing; finally, students also positively perceived the strategy of mind mapping and thought it helped them to better write in English.

Mind mapping is the easiest way to develop information in a human mind and take information out of the brain. It is a creative and effective way that map our ideas. Mind maps can work as a tool to facilitate the learners to plan ideas in the pre-writing process. Learners can be provided with examples to prepare a step wise pattern in a hierarchy that would help them retain ideas till the whole of the essay is written. Mind mapping techniques are good to be applied in the pre-writing stage to explore ideas and generate thoughts on the topic for writing. Mind mapping allows gathering concepts in relation to the main theme. Mind mapping can work as a tool to facilitate the learners to plan ideas in the pre-

writing process. Learners can be provided with examples to prepare a step wise pattern in the hierarchy that would help them retain ideas till the whole of the essay is written. Mind-mapping techniques are good to be applied in the pre-writing stage to explore ideas and generate thoughts on the topic for writing. The mind-mapping technique was effective to help students in writing descriptive texts. Mind mapping could help students to improve their writing skills in writing descriptive text in terms of enriching vocabulary, increasing creativity, arranging sentences, and organizing ideas (Nurlaila, 2013; Alzyoud et al., 2017). As a result, the mind mapping technique would seem to be particularly suited to help students in planning their writing as the approach encourages students to reach for and adapt to a deeper level of understanding of the writing topics. In writing activity students not only give the information to all readers, but students should focus on lexical meaning, focus on ideas, and focus on the meaning of the text that is given to the readers so the text is easy to understand by the readers. Then another problem faced by the students is that students also feel difficulty in constructing the ideas into text. It because of students is a lack of lexical competence and a lack of constructing ideas into good sentences. Therefore, this study aims to find out the effect of the mind mapping technique on students' writing skills at secondary school.

References

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